

variable range of seed set in the indica, indica/japonica, and japonica lines in crosses with indica pollinators may have been due to some genetically controlled incompatibility system, depending upon the degree of affinity between the parental varieties used in this study. Such a system has been reported to explain the intervarietal hybrid sterility in rice. *S*

Diversification of cytoplasmic male sterility in rice

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Segregating lines of crosses between varieties of diverse origin were examined for male steriles occurring naturally.

In six of the seven male steriles isolated, sterility was found to be genetic. Cytological studies of these genetic male steriles showed regular meiosis, indicating pollen abortion in postmeiotic stages.

The other male sterile plant isolated from the F₂ of Ratna/Rajai had multiple pistils and whitish rudimentary anthers. This plant was propagated through stubbles and crosses were made. Spikelet fertility in the F₁s showed three classes of F₁ — completely sterile, partially fertile, and fertile — indicating that male sterility is conditioned by cytoplasmic-genetic factors.

Crosses were made with high yielding donors for resistance to disease and stress. In the F₁ hybrids, most varieties had varying fertility restoration ability. Maintainers of sterility were less common. Of the 40 hybrid combinations studied, only IET4699 and Surekha were identified as maintainers. Ratna, Kalinga III (CR237-1), and IET7302 were strong restorers. Utkal Prava (CR1030), Ta-poo-che-ze, and Rasi were weak maintainers.

Backcrosses with IET4699 and Surekha were made to transfer cytoplasmic sterility into their nuclear background. *S*

Heritability of compact panicle and stigma color

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Heritability of compact and lax panicle was examined in the F₁ and F₂ of a cross of Dee-gee-woo-gen (lax) and BU-I (compact).

BU-I is a mutant isolated from X-ray irradiated NC1626. The compact panicles of this mutant have fewer secondary branches and shorter pedicel,

Table 1. Chi-square analysis of F₂ of Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-I for compact panicle. West Bengal, India.

Panicle trait	Frequency	χ^2 ^a	Ratio
Lax	117	1.696	1:2:1
Intermediate	237		
Compact	102		

^ad.f. = 1 at 5% level = 3.841; at 1% level = 6.635.

Table 2. Analysis of F₂ of 4 crosses for stigma color. West Bengal, India.

Cross	Stigma color	Frequency	χ^2 ^a	Ratio
Dee-gee-woo-gen/BJ-1	Black	440	0.349	3:1
	White	155		
Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-3	Black	232	0.068	3:1
	White	80		
IR8/CRM	Black	910	0.444	3:1
	White	290		
IR8/BU-3	Black	256	0.004	3:1
	White	84		
Pooled	Black	1633	0.325	3:1
	White	529		

^ad.f. = 2 at 5% level = 5.991.

resulting in closely attached spikelets. The primary branches also are closely attached with the main axis of the panicle.

The F₁ hybrids had intermediate panicles, resembling the female parent Dee-gee-woo-gen. The F₂ plants showed 3 distinct panicle types: compact (like BU-I); intermediate (like F₁); and lax (like Dee-gee-woo-gen), in a 1:2:1 ratio (Table 1). This indicates that this panicle character is controlled by a partially dominant gene.

To study stigma color, three strains (BJ-1, CRM6-5-90, BU-3) with black stigma and two strains (Dee-gee-woo-gen, IR8) with white stigma were crossed in these combinations: Dee-gee-woo-gen/BJ-1, Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-3, IR8/CRM-6-5-90, and IR8/BU-3.

In the F₁, all hybrids had black stigma. F₂ plants had black and white stigma in a 3:1 ratio (Table 2). This indicates black stigma is controlled by a single dominant gene independent of apiculus color. *S*

Root systems in hybrid rice

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Chinese scientists reported that strong and active root systems efficiently used applied fertilizers in hybrid rice. We

studied the root system of hybrid rice by the root pulling force method developed at IIRRI. The method assumes a correlation between the force required to pull seedlings or plants and strong, deep root systems which may confer drought tolerance. The results indicated that F₁ hybrids were significantly superior in root pulling force to their parents and check

Table 1. Root pulling force of hybrids, their parents, and check varieties, 1983 summer.

Hybrid, variety	Root pulling force (kg)
<i>F₁ hybrids</i>	
V20A/IR50	24.05*
V20A/IR54	25.15*
Z97A/IR50	23.98*
Z97A/IR54	25.10*
Z97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	22.90*
Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1	24.95*
Mean	24.36
<i>Parents</i>	
IR50	18.15
IR54	22.95
IR2307-247-2-2-3	17.90
IR13420-6-3-3-1	19.43
V20B	14.95
Z97B	17.15
Mean	18.43
<i>Checks</i>	
CR44-35	17.18
Sita	21.43
Mean	19.31
CD at 5%	1.23

varieties (Table 1). The highest root pulling force of 25.15 kg was for V20A/IR54, followed by 25.10 kg for Z97A/IR54 and 24.95 kg Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1.

All *F₁* hybrids showed positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for root pulling force

(Table 2). Highest heterosis and heterobeltiosis values were observed in V20A/IR50 and maximum standard heterosis value in Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1. A strong, deep, and active root system in hybrid rice may also have potential for its adaptation in rainfed uplands and lowlands. *S*

Table 2. Expression of heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for root pulling force, 1983 summer.

Hybrid	Heterosis (%)	Heterobeltiosis (%)	Standard heterosis (%)
V20A/IR50	44.9	32.5	40.0
V20A/IR54	33.1	9.6	17.4
Z97A/IR50	35.5	32.1	39.6
Z97A/IR54	24.9	9.4	17.1
Z97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	30.9	27.9	33.3
Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1	36.4	28.4	45.2

Isolation of fertility restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic genetic male sterile line

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Development of hybrid rice is possible only if the effective fertility restorers for cytoplasmic genetic male sterile (CMS) lines are identified or developed.

Isolation of maintainers for CMS lines is necessary for the development of new CMS lines.

We used the Chinese CMS line V20A as common female parent in crosses

List of complete restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers identified for CMS line V20A at Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, India, 1984.

Complete restorers	Partial restorers	Maintainers
CR289-1208	CR407-6-2	ADT30
CR75-93-Mut. 11-4	CR401-7	Bala
IR9703-4-1-3-3-1	CR167-7	CR407-19
IR2307-247-2-2-3	CR157-22-1900	CR200-788-3
Madhu	IR60	Dhaneshwar
	Pusa 205-15-1	Jikoku Sernai
	RP1451-2266-55-22	MR365
	RP732-26-2	Pusa 2-21
		Ramchure

with standard varieties and elite breeding lines. Percent spikelet fertility of *F₁* hybrids was used as fertility index. Lines that restored 80% or more spikelet fertility were classified as

complete restorers, those restoring between 20% and 79% fertility were partial restorers, and those with less than 20% were classified as maintainers (see table). *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

OTHER PESTS

Reaction of rice varieties to root nematode *Hirschmanniella* spp. in the field

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Seventeen rice varieties were evaluated for resistance to root nematode. The average initial population of *Hirschmanniella* spp. extracted from soil samples of the experimental field before planting was 145 nematodes/300 cc soil.

Each test variety was seeded and transplanted into 3 rows at 25 × 25-cm spacing, 10 hills/row.

At 60 d after transplanting, the final population of nematodes was extracted from soil taken from around the root zone in the middle row of each variety.